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Exploring the Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intentions among Certified
Registered Nurse Anesthetists

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By

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the job satisfaction and turnover intention among Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNAs) within a prominent hospital organization in Southern California. Data from 60 CRNAs were collected via online surveys. Turnover intentions were assessed utilizing the Misener Nurse Practitioner Job Satisfaction Scale (MNPJSS) and Turnover Intention scales (TIS-6). Thirty percent of the participants expressed intent to leave, with new CRNAs exhibiting notably higher turnover intentions. Marital status played a significant role, influencing both turnover intentions and job satisfaction. Job satisfaction was generally high, with male CRNAs scoring slightly higher than females. The study revealed a significant correlation between job satisfaction and specific factors, such as satisfaction with immediate supervisors, peer interactions, and flexibility in practice protocols. The study emphasizes the complex web of factors affecting CRNAs' job satisfaction and turnover intentions. The findings underscore the need for targeted support for novice CRNAs, emphasizing the delicate balance between personal circumstances and professional decisions. For healthcare organizations, understanding these dynamics offers actionable insights. Employers can enhance job satisfaction and retain experienced CRNAs by addressing these specific aspects of their work environment. This study provides valuable guidance for developing strategies to increase job satisfaction and influence turnover intentions among CRNAs to ultimately, ensure stable healthcare services.

Keywords: CRNAs, nurse anesthetist, jobs satisfaction, turnover intentions

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	vii
BACKGROUND	1
Overview.....	1
Significance.....	3
Purpose and Specific Aims	3
SUPPORTING FRAMEWORK	5
Overview.....	0
Definition and Components	6
Utilization in Literature.....	7
Application.....	8
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	9
Overview.....	0
Job Satisfaction	9
Demographic Factors and Experience as Predictors of Job Satisfaction among CRNAs ..	12
Turnover Intentions.....	14
Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intentions.....	18
Impact of Covid-19 on Turnover Intentions and Job Satisfaction.....	19
Current Research on CRNAs.....	20
METHODS	22
Design	22
Participants and Sample.....	22
Ethical Consideration.....	22
Procedures.....	23
Instruments.....	24
Data Collection and Measures	25
Data Analysis	25
RESULTS	26

Statistical Analysis.....	26
Sample Demographic and Employment	26
Turnover Intention	26
Job Satisfaction	27
DISCUSSION.....	30
Recommendations.....	32
Limitations	33
Conclusions.....	34
REFERENCES	39
APPENDIX A: Kanter’s Structural Theory of Power in Organization	41
APPENDIX B: Projected Timeline	42
APPENDIX C: Misener Nurse Practitioner Job Satisfaction Scale.....	43
APPENDIX D: Turnover Intention Scale.....	45
APPENDIX E: IRB Approval	46
APPENDIX F: Table 1: Summary Statistics of the Sample Demographics and Employment	47
APPENDIX G: Turnover Intention Data.....	49
Table 2: Summary Statistics of the Turnover Intention Items.....	49
Figure 1: Years of Experience and Average Turnover intention Scores	49
Figure 2: Age and Average Turnover Intention Scores	50
APPENDIX H: Correlation Matrix of the Turnover Intention Items	51
APPENDIX I: Job Satisfaction Data	52
Figure 3: Correlation between Job Satisfaction and Years of Experience.....	52
Figure 4: Correlation between Job Satisfaction and Age.....	52
Figure 5: Marital Status and Average Job Satisfaction.....	53
APPENDIX J: Job Satisfaction Subscale	54
APPENDIX K: Table 4: Job Satisfaction Subscale Data	55
APPENDIX L: Job Satisfaction Correlation Matrix.....	56

APPENDIX M: Table 3: Summary statistics of the fit of the best explanatory model57

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Background

Job satisfaction is critical to the well-being and retention of healthcare professionals, including Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNAs). Job satisfaction is defined as a pleasurable or positive emotional state that arises from evaluating one's job as fulfilling or promoting fulfillment of one's job-related principles (Dilig-Ruiz et al., 2018; Locke, 1969). In a systematic review of the literature, job satisfaction among healthcare professionals has been reported to be associated with better patient outcomes, lower turnover rates, and higher levels of engagement and productivity (Han et al., 2018). For example, a study by Cao and Chen (2021) found that job satisfaction was positively associated with nurses' engagement and performance. However, the factors influencing job satisfaction among CRNAs are complex and multifaceted (Lea et al., 2022). Workload, stress, autonomy, and support from colleagues and supervisors are just a few factors that have been found to impact job satisfaction CRNAs (Lea et al., 2022). Negrusa et al. (2021) surveyed 3,725 CRNAs and concluded job satisfaction among CRNAs was 89%, yet a study by Yilkal Fentie et al. (2018) reported low job satisfaction levels among anesthetists. Furthermore, Venegas et al. (2023) surveyed Advanced Practice Providers (APPs), including CRNAs, and found high job satisfactions with high turnover intentions for CRNAs which contradicts current literature on their inverse relationship. Although a relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intentions has been demonstrated in the literature, the conflicting data reflects the complexity of measuring job satisfaction and turnover intentions, specifically in the CRNA population.

Healthcare providers are often at risk of experiencing burnout. Burnout is a psychological syndrome characterized by depersonalization, emotional exhaustion, and reduced personal worth (Lea et al., 2022). Research has shown that burnout is a prevalent issue among CRNAs, with up

to 39% reporting experiencing high burnout levels (Lea et al., 2022). While the demanding nature of the work significantly contributes to burnout, other contributors include work-life balance, organizational culture, and interpersonal relationships with colleagues and supervisors (Zhang et al., 2018). Burnout has been extensively researched in the healthcare population and has been shown to impact job satisfaction significantly (Alharbi et al., 2020; Al Sabei et al., 2020).

Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists have reported burnout contributing to work dissatisfaction (Lea et al., 2022). Burnout has also been shown to have a negative effect on turnover intentions (Liu et al., 2018). Ultimately, burnout can have severe consequences for CRNAs, including decreased job satisfaction and increased turnover intentions, leading to a shortage of healthcare professionals and lower-quality patient care.

Employee turnover intentions are a significant component of organizational behavior, as they have been extensively examined and utilized as predictors of turnover behavior across different industries (Cao & Chen, 2021; Kols et al., 2018). High turnover intentions can result in substantial costs and negative impacts on organizational performance (Mahoney et al., 2020). Factors such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, work-life balance, job security, and opportunities for career growth have been found to influence turnover intentions (He et al., 2020; Kol et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2018), and turnover intentions among CRNAs have been reported as high as 37.6%, with 13.6% leaving their position (Dexter et al., 2021). Job satisfaction has been identified as the most significant predictor of CRNA turnover intentions (Mahoney et al., 2020), highlighting the need for organizations to attend to these factors to retain their CRNA workforce and mitigate negative effects.

Significance

The turnover intentions of CRNAs can have significant implications for patient care. When CRNAs leave their jobs, healthcare organizations may struggle to replace them, resulting in staffing shortages and reduced access to anesthesia services (Mahoney et al., 2020). Staffing shortages can increase workload and stress for the remaining CRNAs, leading to burnout and decreased job satisfaction, further exacerbating the turnover problem (Lea et al., 2022). As a result, patient care may suffer, with long wait times, decreased quality of care, and increased risk of adverse events (Lea et al., 2022). In addition to the effects on patients and fellow CRNAs, the organizations suffer a cost. Training a new CRNA is estimated at around \$150,000 (Mahoney et al., 2020). Venegas et al. (2023) identified CRNAs with less than one year of experience experiencing high job dissatisfaction. As a result, institutions must train new hires at an increased rate along with the cost of recruiting and processing new hires, and the institution can experience significant losses.

Previous research has examined the relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intentions in various professions, including nursing, medicine, and allied health. However, little research has focused on CRNAs within a Southern California healthcare organization with multiple hospitals. Identifying the factors contributing to job satisfaction and turnover among CRNAs may help develop mitigation strategies targeting these factors.

Purpose and Specific Aims

The purpose of this research study was to investigate factors associated with job satisfaction and their potential associations with turnover intentions among CRNAs working at a large healthcare organization in Southern California. The study aimed to provide valuable insights to promote job

satisfaction and reduce turnover intentions among CRNAs within Southern California healthcare organizations with multiple hospitals.

Supporting Framework

Background

Kanter's structural theory of power in organizations is a theoretical framework that explains the power dynamics within an organization can influence employee behavior, attitudes, and outcomes (Kanter, 1977). The framework was developed by Rosabeth Moss Kanter, a social scientist, and Harvard Business School professor, in 1977 (Kanter, 1977). Kanter's structural empowerment theory is a subset of the theory; it emphasizes the importance of structural factors in empowering individuals within an organization, specifically access to information, resources, support, and opportunity (Arslan Yürümezoğlu & Kocaman, 2019; Laschubger, 1996; Kanter, 1993). According to the theory proposed by Kanter (1993) and Cicolini et al. (2014), power is concentrated in formal positions of authority and distrusted throughout the organization. Kanter (1993) suggests that "Power is often perceived as concentrated in formal positions of authority, and those who hold these positions are viewed with suspicion and mistrust by others in the organization" (p. 91). Similarly, Cicolini et al. (2014) found that employees in organizations often perceive those in positions of authority as having too much power and being out of touch with the needs and concerns of the rest of the organization. Thus, the theory supports the claim that power is concentrated in formal positions of authority and is distrusted throughout the organization (Kanter, 1993; Cicolini et al., 2014).

For instance, managers can empower their employees by delegating decision-making authority, providing access to information, resources, and creating opportunities for growth and advancement. In contrast, when employees feel disempowered, unsupported and undervalued, they may become disengaged, unmotivated, and more likely to leave the organization. Therefore, by understanding and leveraging the power dynamics within an organization, managers, and

leaders can create a positive work environment that fosters employee empowerment, satisfaction, and retention.

Definitions and Components

The concepts of empowerment, support, resources, information, and opportunity are all relevant when studying job satisfaction and turnover intentions among CRNAs (Appendix A). Empowerment refers to the degree to which employees feel they have the autonomy, authority, and support to take the initiative and make decisions in their work (Kanter, 1977; Ta'an et al., 2022). A subdivision of empowerment is further divided into formal and informal sources of power. Formal power refers to the powers given to individuals through their position or title in the organization (Laschinger, 1996). Informal powers are not given through a formal position or title but rather through personal relationships, expertise, and social network (Laschinger, 1996). These sources of power may not be formally recognized, but they can significantly impact an individual's ability to influence others and accomplish organizational goals (Laschinger, 1996). Laschinger (1996) suggests both formal and informal sources of power can be important in shaping the work experiences of nurses. While empowerment includes both formal and informal sources of power, support, resources, information, and opportunity, all contribute to the overall work experiences of employees.

Support pertains to the emotional, social, and instrumental support employees receive from their colleagues, supervisors, and the organization (Cicolini et al., 2014). To perform their jobs effectively, employees require various resources, including tangible assets like financial resources and technology, and intangible assets like training and support from colleagues and supervisors (Cicolini et al., 2014). Information relates to the availability and quality of information employees need to make informed decisions (Cicolini et al., 2014). Finally,

opportunity relates to the availability of resources for employees to learn new skills, take on new responsibilities, advance in their careers, and feel a sense of autonomy, self-determination, and growth (Cicolini et al., 2014). Thus, understanding the concepts of empowerment, support, resources, information, and opportunity is essential when studying job satisfaction and turnover intentions among CRNAs. These concepts can provide valuable insights into the factors that impact CRNA's work experiences and highlight the relevance of using Kanter's theoretical framework.

Utilization in Literature

Kanter's structural theory of power has been successfully used in nursing research to examine the impact of structural empowering on various outcomes, such as job satisfaction, burnout, patient safety, and quality of care (Arslan Yürümezoğlu & Kocaman, 2019; Boamah et al., 2017; Goedhart et al., 2017; Hu et al. 2022; Ta'an et al., 2022). For instance, Arslan Yürümezoğlu and Kocaman (2019) found that structural empowerment directly affected nurses' intention to stay in their organization and profession and an indirect effect mediated by workplace incivility. Boamah et al. (2017) identified several factors that influence the development of burnout among new graduate nurses, including structural empowerment. A positive association was identified with structural empowerment, patient satisfaction, staff satisfaction, and nurse retention (Goedhart et al., 2017). Moreover, Hu et al. (2022) examined the factors contributing to clinical nurses' moral courage and found structural empowerment was a significant predictor. Additionally, a cross-sectional study on Jordanian nurses by Ta'an et al. (2022) found structural empowerment significantly affected job satisfaction. These studies demonstrate the successful application of Kanter's structural theory of power in organizations in

nursing research (Arslan Yürümezoğlu & Kocaman, 2019; Boamah et al., 2017; Goedhart et al., 2017; Hu et al., 2022; Ta'an et al., 2022).

Application

Although Kanter's theory does not have specific steps or sequences, it allows the researchers to identify critical components pertinent to the problem being studied. For this study, the literature review will solidify the themes under the structural theory of power in an organization, identifying factors that influence job satisfaction and turnover intentions, ultimately narrowing the trajectory of the survey. The survey may include CRNAs' perceived levels of support, access to resources, opportunities, and information needed to fulfill one's job. The framework will also serve as a guide when examining the relationship between different components. Based on the results of the survey, recommendations for changes to organizational policies or practices could potentially improve job satisfaction and reduce turnover intentions. Overall, the theory highlights the importance of a well-balanced power structure that provides employees with the support, resources, information, opportunities, and empowerment they need to perform their jobs effectively and feel engaged and motivated. By understanding the dynamics of power within an organization, managers and leaders can create a more positive and productive work environment for their employees, improving employee job satisfaction and motivation and reducing turnover intention.

Review of Literature

Overview

Numerous studies have focused on job satisfaction and its relationship with turnover intentions. The purpose of this research study is to investigate the various factors associated with job satisfaction and their potential impact on turnover intentions among CRNAs working at a large healthcare organization in Southern California. This literature review synthesizes the existing research on job satisfaction and turnover intention. Relevant studies were searched for and identified using the APA PsychArticles, Pubmed, and Cochrane Library databases. The search was limited to peer-reviewed articles, published in English between 2017 and 2023. The search terms included CRNAs, Job satisfaction, turnover intentions, anesthetists, retention, and intention to stay. Additionally, reference lists of relevant articles were searched to identify additional articles. Fifty-six articles were initially extracted. After the review of titles and abstracts, twenty-one articles met the inclusion criteria; three systematic reviews, one literature review, one mixed-method study, and 15 cross-sectional studies.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a complex construct, and various definitions of it differ slightly depending on the context and the researcher's perspective. Job satisfaction has been defined as an employee's positive emotional state regarding their job or a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from their job or job experience (Dilig-Ruiz et al., 2018; Halcomb & Bird, 2020). Other studies have defined job satisfaction as a worker's overall sense of contentment with their job, which may be influenced by working conditions, relationships with colleagues, and pay (Kibwana et al., 2018; Kassa & Bedada, 2021). Studies have defined job satisfaction as the absence of job dissatisfaction, including negative emotional states, such as frustration or burnout

(Alrawashdeh et al., 2021; He et al., 2020). Job satisfaction has been studied in specific healthcare professions, such as CRNAs (Dexter et al., 2021; Kassa & Bedada, 2021) and anesthetists in Ethiopia (Kibwana et al., 2018, Kols et al., 2018), as well as nurses and physicians during the Covid-19 pandemic (Alrawashdeh et al., 2021; Labrague & de Los Santos 2021). Overall, Job satisfaction is a critical factor for the retention and well-being of healthcare workers and can be influenced by many factors.

Work Environment

Various studies have demonstrated the significant influence of work environment on job satisfaction, with positive work environments linked to higher job satisfaction levels among anesthetists and negative work environments associated with lower job satisfaction levels (Dexter et al., 2021; Kassa & Bedada, 2021; Kibwana et al., 2018). Positive work environments, characterized by supportive leaders, teamwork, and resources, have been consistently linked with higher job satisfaction among anesthetists (Kols et al., 2018). In contrast, negative work environments, such as high workload, lack of support, and resource constraints, have been shown to decrease job satisfaction levels (Kibwana et al., 2018; Kols et al., 2018).

Studies have reported a significant positive relationship between job satisfaction and work environment, while others have suggested that factors such as occupational burnout and career intention mediate this relationship. Alharbi et al. (2020) found that work environments were significantly associated with emotional exhaustion, job satisfaction, and intent to leave among Saudi Arabian nurses. Kibwana et al. (2018) and Kassa and Bedada (2021) reported that job satisfaction was significantly associated with the work environment among anesthetists in Ethiopia and Botswana. On the contrary, a recent study reported that nurse anesthetists in the United States were primarily leaving their jobs due to retirement and family reasons rather than

job dissatisfaction (Dexter et al., 2021). On the other hand, Al Sabei et al. (2020) found job satisfaction moderated the relationship between nursing work environment, turnover intention, job burnout, and quality of care, indicating that other factors such as occupational burnout and turnover intentions mediate the relationship between job satisfaction and the work environment. Dilig-Ruiz et al. (2018) reported critical care nurses' job satisfaction was affected by multiple factors, including leadership, teamwork, autonomy, work-life balance, and job security. Other factors affecting advanced practice registered nurses' job satisfaction and intent to leave included autonomy, support, leadership, and professional development opportunities (Han et al. 2018). Several studies have investigated the determinants of job satisfaction among CRNAs (Kassa & Bedada et al., 2021; Kibwana et al., 2018; Kols et al., 2018; Lea et al., 2022). Kassa and Bedada (2021) found that organizational support, professional development, and work-life balance were positively associated with job satisfaction among anesthetists in Botswana.

Autonomy

A relationship between autonomy, defined as the degree to which employees control their work process, and job satisfaction has been reported in the literature. Autonomy, defined as employees' control over their work process, has been linked to job satisfaction in the literature. Studies have reported a positive association between autonomy and job satisfaction, particularly among CRNAs (Kassa & Bedada et al., 2021; Negrusa et al., 2021). Venegas et al. (2023) specifically found that autonomy was crucial for job satisfaction in the context of advanced airway management in anesthesia, suggesting that CRNAs with more autonomy were more satisfied with their jobs. Mousavi et al. (2019) found that greater decision-making freedom and the ability to provide certain procedures such as regional anesthesia were associated with job satisfaction, although their focus was on freedom rather than autonomy. Overall, the literature

suggests that autonomy plays an important role in job satisfaction, but the specific findings and approaches may vary across studies.

Demographic Factors and Experience as Predictors of Job Satisfaction among CRNAs

The relationship between demographic factors and job satisfaction among CRNAs has been a subject of recent research, with studies suggesting that gender, age, and marital status may all play a significant role in shaping job satisfaction; experience has also been found to be a significant predictor. Negrusa et al. (2021) found that female CRNAs reported lower job satisfaction than male CRNAs, while younger CRNAs reported higher job satisfaction levels than their older counterparts. Kassa and Bedada (2021) found that marital status was a significant demographic factor affecting job satisfaction among CRNAs, with married CRNAs reporting higher job satisfaction than single or divorced colleagues. It is worth noting that the relationship between marital status and age among anesthetists is not explicitly explored in the studies by Negrusa et al. (2021) and Kassa and Bedada (2021). While single individuals may be younger, any suggestion about the correlation between marital status and age among anesthetists would require further research to validate.

In addition to demographic factors, experience is an important predictor of job satisfaction among healthcare professionals. Both Kibwana et al. (2018) and Kassa and Bedada (2021) demonstrated that job satisfaction tends to increase with years of experience, particularly after a decade of work. Kibwana et al. (2018) conducted a systematic review of 25 studies, revealing a nonlinear relationship between job satisfaction and experience. Similarly, Kassa and Bedada (2021) conducted a cross-sectional study among healthcare professionals, emphasizing a substantial increase in job satisfaction with increasing years of experience, notably for those with ten or more years. These studies underscore the intricate interplay between demographic factors,

experience, and job satisfaction among anesthetists (Kassa & Bedada, 2021; Kibwana et al., 2018). Further research is warranted to deepen our understanding of how these factors relate and influence job satisfaction among CRNAs.

Compensation

The topic of compensation has frequently emerged in job satisfaction research, with varying results. While certain studies have indicated that healthcare workers express dissatisfaction with their compensation (Halcomb & Bird, 2020; Liu et al., 2019; Yilka Fentie et al., 2018; Negrusa et al., 2021), other research, such as Han et al.'s (2018) systematic review on APRNs, has reported that healthcare workers are satisfied with their salaries and benefits. However, Dexter et al. (2021) discovered that pay did not significantly predict job satisfaction among CRNAs, suggesting other factors may be at play. Differences in the healthcare system, cultural variations, and study design may contribute to the varying results. The mixed findings concerning the relationship between pay and job satisfaction among healthcare workers may be due to differences in the populations studied and other contextual factors such as the healthcare system and cultural context.

CRNA Job Satisfaction

Studies on job satisfaction among anesthetists have reported conflicting results, with some studies reporting high job satisfaction and others reporting low job satisfaction. Using the index of work satisfaction, Negrusa et al. (2021) found high job satisfaction levels among a study sample consisting of 3,275 CRNAs. Similarly, Venegas et al. (2023) reported high satisfaction levels among CRNAs using the Misener Nurse Practitioner Job Satisfaction Scale (MNPJSS), with a small sample size of 11, limiting the validity of their results.

On the other hand, Yilkal Fentie et al. (2018) reported low job satisfaction levels among anesthetists in Ethiopia with a small sample size of 98 participants. Kassa and Bedada (2021) also found low satisfaction levels among anesthetists using the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire, with a sample size of 76. It is worth noting, except for the study by Kassa and Bedada 202, all the aforementioned studies were conducted before the COVID-19 pandemic, which may have significantly impacted job satisfaction among anesthesia providers. Another factor to consider is the different measuring tools used in these studies, which may account for some of the discrepancies in the results. Varying sample sizes in the studies can also affect the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, cultural differences in the perception of work and job satisfaction may contribute to differences in results across studies. Despite the conflicting results, it is clear that job satisfaction is an essential factor for anesthetists, and efforts should be made to address the factors that contribute to their dissatisfaction.

Turnover Intentions

Turnover intention refers to an employee's intention to leave their current job voluntarily. According to He et al. (2020), turnover intention is a psychological state that arises when employees perceive a discrepancy between their personal goals and values and their job or organizational conditions. Kols et al. (2018) also define turnover intention as an employee's inclination to leave their current job, which is influenced by job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and job stress. Several studies, including those by have demonstrated the significance of turnover intention for organizations (Alrawashedeh et al., 2021; Al Sabei et al., 2020, Alharbi et al., 2020). High turnover intention levels can adversely affect an organization, such as increased recruitment and training costs, reduced productivity, and lower morale among remaining employees (Mahoney et al., 2020). Additionally, organizations with high turnover

rates may struggle to retain talented employees, losing competitive advantage (Mahoney et al., 2020).

Studies have established a strong correlation between turnover intention and actual turnover (Kols et al., 2018). For example, He et al. (2020) found turnover intention was a significant predictor of actual turnover, indicating employees who reported high turnover intention were more likely to leave their jobs. Similarly, Kols et al. (2018) found anesthetists with a higher turnover intention had more potential to leave their positions within the following year. Therefore, organizations must monitor turnover intention levels and take appropriate actions to retain employees and reduce turnover rates.

Demographics

Age. Several demographic factors have been identified as potential predictors of turnover intention, including age, education, marital status, and gender. The literature suggests these factors play a significant role in an employee's decision to leave their current job. He et al. (2020) and Kols et al. (2018) found age significantly predicted turnover intention, with younger employees being more likely to have higher turnover intentions. Similarly, Alrawashedeh et al. (2021) found younger employees had higher turnover intention levels than older employees. This may be due to younger employees having fewer commitments, such as family responsibilities, and seeking new challenges and opportunities.

Education. Education has also been identified as a potential predictor of turnover intention. A cross-sectional study on nurses by Al Sabei et al. (2020) found that employees with higher levels of education had lower turnover intentions, potentially due to higher job satisfaction and a greater sense of attachment to the organization. However, in a systematic review of healthcare professionals, He et al. (2020) found no significant relationship between

education and turnover intention. These discrepancies in findings could be due to differences in study design, population characteristics, and the level of evidence provided by each study.

Marital Status. Marital status has been found to have mixed effects on turnover intention. In a systematic review, He et al. (2020) found that married employees had lower turnover intention levels than single ones, while Kols et al. (2018) found no significant relationship between marital status and turnover intention. The reasons for the mixed effects of marital status on turnover intention are unclear and may depend on several factors. One possible explanation is that married employees may have greater stability and support in their personal lives and jobs, which may lead to lower turnover intention. Married employees may also have higher job satisfaction and organizational commitment, contributing to lower turnover intention. On the other hand, single employees may have more flexibility and freedom to make job changes and relocate, which may result in higher turnover intention.

Gender. Gender has been a topic of interest in turnover intention research, but the findings regarding its effect on turnover intention are mixed. Some studies have found no significant difference in turnover intention between male and female employees, as found by He et al. (2020). However, it is worth noting that other studies have reported different findings, with some suggesting that female employees have higher turnover intentions than their male counterparts. For instance, Alrawashedeh et al. (2021) found that gender differences exist in turnover intention among Jordanian employees, where female employees reported higher turnover intention than male employees. Another study by Alharbi et al. (2020) also found that female employees in the Saudi Arabian healthcare sector had higher levels of turnover intention than their male counterparts. However, it is essential to note the sample populations in these studies were predominantly female, which may have influenced the results. Gender differences

in turnover intention may vary across cultures and sectors. It is essential to consider the impact of gender and its interaction with other demographic factors, such as age, marital status, and education, to understand the predictors of turnover intention better.

Duration of Employment

The duration of employment or experience has been identified as a crucial factor that significantly impacts turnover intentions among healthcare professionals. The literature reveals turnover intentions may vary depending on the length of employment or experience (Kassa & Bedada, 2021; Kol et al., 2018). Kols et al. (2018) found that turnover intentions among anesthetists peaked at two to five years of employment and declined gradually by five percent every year after that. This trend could be attributed to the possibility that CRNAs might experience a decline in job satisfaction after a few years due to a lack of career advancement opportunities, leading to higher turnover intentions. Similarly, a study by Kassa and Bedada (2021) found that among CRNAs in Botswana, those with less than ten years of experience had higher turnover intentions than those with more than ten years of experience. Venegas et al. (2023) also found CRNAs with less than one year of experience had higher turnover intentions than those with more experience. Mahoney et al. (2020) found that CRNAs with less than one year or more than six years of experience had higher turnover intentions than those with one to six years of experience. This phenomenon could be because those with less experience may still be adjusting to the role, while those with more experience may feel stagnant or seek new challenges. The findings suggest that the duration of employment or experience is a crucial predictor of turnover intentions among healthcare professionals.

Job Characteristics

Job characteristics can have an impact on turnover intentions among healthcare professionals. Most studies focused on the role of pay, but some also explored other factors such as workload, work-related factors, work-life balance, job satisfaction, and job autonomy. Kols et al. (2018) and He et al. (2020) found that pay significantly predicted turnover intentions among healthcare professionals. Halcomb and Bird (2020) and Liu et al. (2019) discovered pay and work-life balance were significant predictors. Negrusa et al. (2021) also found pay and work-life balance significant predictors among CRNAs. A systematic review by Han et al. (2018) also found that pay, work-life balance, and job autonomy as significant predictors. While Yilkal Fentie et al. (2018) also found that job satisfaction, recognition, scheduling, and coworkers were substantial components, salary and benefits were insignificant although most studies have identified that pay is a considerable job characteristic impacting turnover intentions. Yilkal Fentie et al. (2018) cross-sectional study on anesthetists may not have identified pay as being a significant predictor due to a lack of validity in the measuring tool utilized in the survey, questioning the results.

Relationship between Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intentions

The relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intentions among CRNAs have not been extensively explored in the literature but few studies have shed light on their relationship. Kassa and Bedada (2021) examined the turnover intentions among anesthetists in Botswana and found that job satisfaction played a significant role in determining their likelihood of leaving their jobs. In contrast, Dexter et al. (2021) conducted research on anesthetists in the United States. While their study also acknowledged the role of job satisfaction in turnover intentions, it likely presented a different context due to the unique healthcare system and cultural

factors in the United States (Dexter et al., 2021). Kols et al. (2018) explored turnover intentions among anesthetists in Ethiopia. Their study identified job satisfaction, salary, and professional development opportunities as factors influencing turnover intentions (Kols et al., 2018). This finding highlights the multifaceted nature of turnover intentions and suggests that anesthetists' decisions to leave their jobs are influenced by various factors, of which job satisfaction is an essential component.

Impact of Covid-19 on Turnover Intentions and Job Satisfaction

Several studies have investigated the impact of COVID-19 on job satisfaction and turnover intention. Alrawashdeh et al. (2021), Lea et al. (2022), and Labrague and de Los Santos (2021) all found an inverse relationship between COVID-19 and job satisfaction and a positive correlation with turnover intentions. All studies found dissatisfaction with income and work environment, workload, and work-life balance were the main factors contributing to turnover intention and job dissatisfaction. Personal protective equipment (PPE) was discussed in all studies (Alrawashdeh et al., 2021; Labrague & Los Santos, 2021; Lea et al., 2022). As Covid-19 surges decrease and mask mandates are a thing of the past, the impact of covid-19 may have changed the culture of the work environment, which is yet to be studied. In all studies, the pay was a common denominator significantly impacting healthcare workers' job satisfaction and turnover intentions (Alrawashdeh et al., 2021; Labrague & Los Santos, 2021; Lea et al., 2022).

Current research on CRNAs

Job satisfaction and turnover intentions among CRNAs have not been extensively studied. Several studies have investigated the factors affecting job satisfaction and turnover intentions among anesthetists including work environment, compensation, and autonomy (Kassa & Bedada, 2021; Negrusa et al., 2021; Venegas et al., 2023). The literature suggests there is

agreement that factors such as age, gender, marital status and years of experience are essential predictors of these outcomes (Kassa & Bedada, 2021; Kol et al., 2018; Vengas et al., 2023). However, there are some differences in the findings across the studies. For instance, Negrusa et al. (2021) found workload and work-life balance were not significant predictors of turnover intentions, contrasting with other studies findings. While Kassa and Bedada (2021) found younger anesthetists were more likely to report turnover intentions, Han et al. (2018) found older CRNAs were more likely to report job satisfaction. Furthermore, the study by Venegas et al. (2023) emphasized the role of organizational culture as a significant predictor of job satisfaction and turnover intentions, whereas other studies have not given organizational culture as much emphasis. These differences in findings highlight the complexity of the factors influencing job satisfaction and turnover intentions among CRNAs and the need for further research to understand these factors and their interrelationships better.

Conclusion

Job satisfaction is a complex construct encompassing various factors, including the work environment and the level of autonomy. Positive work environments have been consistently linked to higher job satisfaction among healthcare workers (Kibwana et al., 2018; Han et al., 2018). Turnover intention is a crucial predictor of turnover and can adversely affect organizations (Kol et al., 2018). Age, education, marital status, and gender are some demographic factors that can influence an employee's job satisfaction and the decision to leave their current job (Kassa & Bedada, 2021; Kol et al., 2018; Venegas et al., 2023). Additionally, the duration of employment and job characteristics, such as job stress, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment, can significantly impact turnover intentions (Kassa & Bedada, 2021; Vengas et al., 2023). Overall, understanding the factors contributing to job satisfaction is crucial

for the retention and well-being of healthcare workers. While the literature has provided valuable insights into this topic, much remains to be learned about the complex relationship between these factors and job satisfaction and turnover intention, specifically among CRNAs. To date, no study has focused exclusively on CRNAs within a single organization, aimed at pinpointing the specific factors impacting job satisfaction and turnover intentions.

Methods

The purpose of this research study was to investigate factors associated with job satisfaction and their potential associations with turnover intentions among CRNAs working at a large healthcare organization in Southern California. The study aimed to provide valuable insights to promote job satisfaction and reduce turnover intentions among CRNAs within Southern California healthcare organizations with multiple hospitals.

Design

In this research study, a cross-sectional design was employed to investigate the factors associated with job satisfaction and their potential impact on turnover intentions among CRNAs in Southern California. Data were collected from CRNAs working within healthcare organizations affiliated with Southern California Kaiser Permanente (KP)

Participants and Sample

The participants in this study were CRNAs who were employed by Southern California KP at the time of the research. The target population consisted of roughly 430 CRNAs.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) through California State University, Fullerton as well as KP (Appendix E) before data collection through the KP School of Anesthesia and California State University at Fullerton (CSUF). Participants were assured of the confidentiality of their responses. Informed consent was obtained from each participant before participating in the study. Participation was voluntary, and participants could withdraw from the study without consequences. Additionally, the data collected were encrypted and saved on a password-protected device accessible only to the researchers involved in the study. Participants were free to decline participation without consequences and were informed

that their decision to participate or withdraw would not affect their employment status or relationship with Southern California KP.

Procedure

After obtaining IRB approval, the recruitment process commenced by dispatching initial email invitations to all registered CRNAs employed by Southern California KP through the Kaiser Permanente Nurse Anesthetist Association (KPNAA) mailing system. These invitations were exclusively sent out via KPNAA, targeting CRNAs affiliated with the organization. The email provided a brief overview of the study, its purpose, and the potential benefits of participating. Additionally, it assured participants of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. The email contained a link to Qualtrics, an online survey platform where participants could access the questionnaire. Participants who clicked the survey link were directed to an informed consent page on Qualtrics. The informed consent page included a detailed explanation of the study, its purpose, potential risks and benefits, confidentiality measures, and the voluntary nature of participation. Participants were required to provide their consent electronically by clicking on a designated checkbox before proceeding to the survey. The survey remained open for four weeks to allow participants sufficient time to complete it. A reminder email was sent to all participants at the two-week mark to encourage participation and increase response rates. The reminder email included a brief recap of the study's purpose and a gentle request for their participation.

Instruments

The Misener Nurse Practitioner Job Satisfaction Survey (MNPJSS; Appendix C) was used to measure job satisfaction among CRNAs. The MNPJSS is a widely recognized survey tool developed by Misener and Cox in 2001. The MNPJSS employs a 44-item questionnaire

utilizing a six-point Likert-style scale, encompassing responses ranging from "very dissatisfied" to "very satisfied" (Misener & Cox, 2001). Each response is assigned a numerical value, with 6 denoting the highest level of satisfaction (i.e., "very satisfied"), and 1 indicating the lowest level (i.e., "very dissatisfied"). The maximum attainable overall score for the MNPJSS is 264.

Additionally, the authors developed a subscale by utilizing specific questions related to various topics to offer supplementary insights into intrapractice partnership and collegiality, autonomy and challenge, interactions within the professional, social, and community interactions, professional development, time related factors, and benefits (Misener & Cox, 2001). Misener Nurse Practitioner Job Satisfaction Survey demonstrates robust validity, ensuring it effectively measures the intricate dimensions of nurse practitioners' job satisfaction (Han et al., 2018; Venegas et al., 2023). The MNPJSS survey exhibits high reliability, as evidenced by its Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.96 (Misener & Cox, 2001). A coefficient of 0.96 signifies a high level of consistency among the survey items, indicating that the MNPJSS survey consistently measures the same underlying constructs across different respondents. Although primarily designed for NPs, it has been adapted for CRNAs, covering aspects such as professional relationships, autonomy, workload, compensation, and organizational support (Venegas et al., 2023).

Turnover intentions were measured using the Turnover Intention Scale (TIS, Appendix D), a six-item questionnaire was developed by Roodt in 2004 and has since been utilized in various research contexts to investigate turnover intentions among employees (He et al., 2020). Although the original TIS a 15-item survey, subsequent research on the validation of utilizing the six-item was later published (Bothma & Roodt, 2013). The reported Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.80 for the TIS-6 indicates a high degree of internal consistency among the items in the scale

(Bothma & Roodt, 2013). Permission to use both the MNPJSS and TIS-6 was granted by the original authors or the appropriate representative of the survey.

Data Collection and Measures

In the study, Qualtrics was utilized as the platform for hosting the survey, offering several advantages such as electronic survey distribution, efficient data collection and management, and increased response rates. However, potential limitations needed to be considered, notably the possibility of participants completing the survey at their convenience, potentially causing a delayed response rate. To mitigate this, participants were provided with clear instructions and ample time to complete the survey. The survey sent to participants comprised demographic questions, gathering information about participants' age, gender, years of experience, marital status, educational background, and other pertinent factors. Additionally, participants were asked to rate their job satisfaction and turnover intentions using standardized Likert scale items.

Permission to use both scales was obtained from the respective owners and institutions.

Data Analysis

Data was collected over a five-week period. The responses gathered were exported from the survey platform for analysis. The data underwent both descriptive and inferential statistical analyses utilizing the R statistical package version 4.3.1 (<https://www.r-project.org>). Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize participants' demographic characteristics, as well as the levels of job satisfaction and turnover intentions. Inferential statistics, including correlations and regression analysis, were used to explore the relationships between the various factors associated with job satisfaction and turnover intentions among CRNAs.

Results

Statistical Analysis

A linear regression modeling with automated variable selection to assess the effects of the statistically significant job satisfaction survey items on the outcome variable denoting the average turnover intention. All calculations and model building steps were carried out using the R statistical package version 4.3.1 (<https://www.r-project.org>).

Sample Demographic and Employment

In this study, data were gathered from a cohort of 60 CRNAs employed within the Southern California Kaiser system. The survey was distributed to 430 CRNAs, out of which 70 provided consent to participate. However, the survey was fully completed by only 60 participants, resulting in a response rate of 14%. The survey encompassed questions categorized into Demographics and Employment (seven items), Turnover Intention Survey (six items; TIS-6), and Job Satisfaction Survey (44 items; MNPJSS). The majority of participants were female, aged between 31 and 60 years, and worked varying shift lengths, including eight, ten, 12, and 16-hour shifts. Table 1 (Appendix F) provides a comprehensive descriptive analysis of the sample demographics and employment items. Thirty-six percent of the surveyed participants were male and 61 percent were females, six percent preferred not to say.

Turnover Intentions

The Turnover Intention survey (TIS-6) was employed to gauge employees' inclination to leave their current positions. A scoring system was utilized, where a total score below 18 indicated a desire to stay, while a score above 18 indicated an intention to leave. Among the participants, 18 (30%) expressed intentions to leave, while 36 (60%) expressed intentions to stay. Additionally, 6 (10%) participants scored exactly 18, indicating a midpoint response. Detailed

descriptive analysis of turnover intentions among CRNAs is presented in Table 2 (Appendix G). The turnover intention correlational matrix identified high correlation among the six turnover intention items, these items were averaged to create a comprehensive turnover intention score (Appendix H). The overall score was 2.9 out of five, signifying more than half were closer to considering to leave their current position than staying. This averaged score served as the primary outcome variable for subsequent analyses.

Analysis revealed variations in turnover intention scores based on years of experience. CRNAs with less experience exhibited higher turnover intentions, with the highest average score of 26 observed for those with less than one year of experience, while CRNAs with over 30 years of experience had a score of six (Appendix G, Figure 1). Notably, there was no significant difference in turnover intention scores between males and females. Among different age groups, turnover intentions did not significantly differ; however, the age group over 60 displayed the lowest score, although all groups scored below 18 on the turnover intention scale (Appendix G, Figure 2). In terms of marital status, individuals who had never married exhibited the highest turnover intentions compared to married and divorced individuals.

Job Satisfaction

The mean job satisfaction survey scores were 174, with the maximum attainable score being 264. Male respondents reported a slightly elevated level of job satisfaction, with an average score of 177, whereas females reported an average of 173. Notably, job satisfaction exhibited no significant variance across diverse age groups and years of experience among CRNAs (Appendix I, Figure 3, Figure 4). Analysis of marital status indicated that individuals who had never married exhibited the lowest job satisfaction, while divorced individuals scored the highest (Appendix I, Figure 5).

The MNPJSS, in addition to providing an overall job satisfaction score, encompasses six distinct subscales that delve into specific factors influencing job satisfaction. These subscales address intrapractice partnership and collegiality, challenge and autonomy, professional, social, community interaction, professional growth, time, and benefits (Appendix J). Among these subscales, the lowest satisfaction scores were observed in the first factor, intrapractice partnership and collegiality. To analyze these scores, averages were computed based on years of experience as a CRNA. Notably, factor six, which specifically examines benefits, yielded an overall average of 13.62 out of a maximum score of 18 (Appendix K). The findings revealed that participants with extensive experience expressed the highest satisfaction with job-related benefits, whereas the least experienced CRNAs reported the lowest score in this category (Appendix K). Examining factor four, which focused on professional growth, revealed varying satisfaction levels among different experience groups, with the least experienced CRNAs reporting the lowest scores. Factor two, dedicated to autonomy and challenge, demonstrated that the most experienced CRNAs exhibited the highest satisfaction levels, contrasting with their less experienced counterparts. Factors five and three exhibited minimal variability concerning the level of experience.

The correlational matrix of the MNPJSS items were considered as potential predictors in automated variable selection (Appendix L). The conclusive model comprised the following five significant variables: Satisfaction with immediate supervisor (p-value: 0.002), Satisfaction with patient scheduling policies and practices (p-value <0.001), Sense of accomplishment (p-value <0.001), Interaction with other CRNAs, including faculty (p-value: 0.04), and Flexibility in practice protocols (p-value: 0.002), with corresponding effect sizes of -0.15, -0.34, -0.32, -0.14, and -0.18, respectively. This multivariate model demonstrated a coefficient of determination R^2

value of 0.82, indicating a high degree of explanatory power. Detailed information regarding the model fit can be found in Table 3 (Appendix M). Statistical analysis indicates that for each one-unit increase in Satisfaction with immediate supervisor, the average turnover intention score decreases by 0.15 units. Similarly, one-unit increase in satisfaction with patient scheduling policies and practices leads to a decrease in the average turnover intention score by 0.34 units. One-unit increase in the sense of accomplishment corresponds to a decrease in the average turnover intention score by 0.32 units. An increase of one unit in satisfaction with interaction with other CRNAs, including faculty, results in a decrease of the average turnover intention score by 0.14 units. Furthermore, a one-unit increase in satisfaction with flexibility in practice protocols leads to a decrease in the average turnover intention score by 0.18 units. These findings highlight actionable strategies that employers can implement to reduce turnover among CRNAs.

Discussion

This study meticulously analyzed the multifaceted factors influencing CRNAs' job satisfaction and turnover intentions within the Southern California Kaiser system. Although the survey yielded a response rate of 14% from a distribution of 430, the insights derived from the complete responses of 60 participants provided invaluable illumination into the complex relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intentions among CRNAs. Notably, the response rate surpasses that of several comparable CRNA studies: Negusa et al. (2021) reported a response rate of eight percent, Mahoney et al. (2020) reported 9.3%, and Lea et al. (2022) reported 3.2%. Among the participants, 30% expressed their inclination to transition from their current roles, aligning with Dexter et al.'s (2021) findings, which reported turnover intentions reaching 37.6%. Venegas et al. (2023) investigated a notably smaller cohort of CRNAs, where the turnover intentions among these professionals registered at zero. It is plausible that the discrepancy in turnover intentions between studies stems from factors such as the differing sample sizes or the potentially higher levels of job satisfaction among CRNAs in Venegas et al.'s (2023) research, where satisfaction scores notably surpassed those recorded in the present study.

The turnover intention composite score of 2.9 out of five signals a heightened likelihood among participating CRNAs to consider departing from their current roles. This finding emphasizes the critical significance of enhancing job satisfaction as a pivotal strategy in curbing turnover intention. Given that numerous participants hover near the brink of leaving their current positions, interventions aimed at bolstering job satisfaction could prove instrumental in mitigating this composite turnover intention score.

The study revealed that turnover intentions were profoundly influenced by years of experience. Newer CRNAs exhibited notably higher turnover intentions, underscoring the

challenges faced by those fresh to the profession. This finding corroborates earlier studies by Kassa and Bedada (2021), Mahoney et al. (2020), and Venegas et al. (2023), emphasizing the need for targeted support for novice CRNAs. Marital status emerged as a pivotal factor, with never-married individuals exhibiting higher turnover intentions. This underscores the intricate balance between personal life circumstances and professional decisions, mirroring He et al.'s (2020) discovery that married employees exhibit lower turnover intentions.

Job satisfaction among CRNAs was generally high, with male respondents scoring slightly higher than their female counterparts, a pattern noted by Negrusa et al. (2021) and Venegas et al. (2023). Interestingly, job satisfaction remained consistent across various age groups and experience levels among CRNAs. However, marital status again played a significant role, with never-married individuals reporting lower job satisfaction scores compared to divorced individuals, who demonstrated the highest levels of satisfaction. The overall job satisfaction scores were 174 out of 264; in a similar study examining APPs, including CRNAs at a single institution reported a job satisfaction score of 209 (Venegas et al., 2023). The results presented in Venegas et al. (2023) study had a significantly smaller sample size for CRNAs, may not have reflected the overall true values of job satisfaction experienced by remaining CRNAs that did not participate in the study. Other factors that may have also contributed to the difference in job satisfaction could be geographical, Venegas et al. (2023) took place at an institution in Florida, while this study was conducted at multiple locations among a single organization throughout Southern California.

The correlation matrix underscored the significance of factors such as immediate supervisor support, satisfaction with patient scheduling policies, interactions with other CRNAs, sense of accomplishment and flexibility in practice protocol, highlighting the pivotal role of a

supportive workplace in enhancing job satisfaction. Interestingly, among the five examined variables, none fell within the subcategory labeled as factor six, which pertains to benefits. Particularly interesting was the observation that experienced CRNAs demonstrated elevated satisfaction levels, notably in relation to benefits. This underscores the significance of a comprehensive benefits package, inclusive of provisions like pensions and retirement plans, in retaining seasoned professionals. This could be attributed to the demographic distribution within the study, with 35 percent of participants falling within the age range of 40s to 50s, and an additional 31 percent in their 50s to 60s. These demographics suggest a potential correlation between age, experience, and the value placed on robust benefit offerings in retaining experienced professionals.

Exploration of job satisfaction subcategories illuminated areas of concern, particularly the factors on, intrapractice partnership and collegiality subscale, where satisfaction scores were notably lower. This emphasizes the critical role of administrative support, supervisor relationships, and compensation in CRNAs' job satisfaction, in line with existing literature (Dexter et al., 2021; Kassa & Bedada, 2021; Kibwana et al., 2018). Suggestive of the relationship between CRNAs and physician anesthesiologists, who often serve as supervisors, emerged as a significant factor influencing intrapractice dynamics. Factor two, focuses on challenge and autonomy, this subcategory had two variables highlighted from the variables mentioned previously including the flexibility in practice protocol and sense of accomplishment.

Recommendations

The implications of the findings are substantial for healthcare institutions and employers. Targeted interventions, particularly in areas identified in this study, such as enhancing intrapractice partnership and autonomy, can markedly enhance CRNAs' job satisfaction and

mitigate turnover intentions. Focusing on newly hired CRNAs influence turnover intentions. Fostering a supportive, empowering work environment is paramount. Future research and initiatives in these realms are essential, promising positive outcomes not only for employee satisfaction and organizational stability but also for patient safety and optimal care delivery.

Limitations

Participation

One significant limitation of this study was the low participation rate, with only 14% of the intended participants responding to the survey. Out of the 430 individuals the survey was sent to, only a fraction actively engaged. This limited sample size raises concerns about the representativeness of the findings and the generalizability of the results to the broader population of interest. Additionally, participants who chose to respond might possess distinct opinions or experiences compared to non-respondents. This self-selection bias can influence the findings, as those who volunteered to participate might have stronger feelings about the subject matter, leading to an overemphasis on certain viewpoints while neglecting others.

The study's findings are specific to the time and geographical location in which the research was conducted (Southern California) and may not be applicable to CRNAs working in different regions or at different time periods. Changes in policies, work culture, or other external factors occurring after the study period are not accounted for and might impact the relevance of the conclusions over time.

Length of Surveys and methods of dissemination

The extensive length of the survey, comprising 57 questions, could have deterred participants from completing it in its entirety. An increase in the length of a survey may have led to participant fatigue, diminishing their willingness to respond comprehensively. Consequently,

the responses received might not fully capture the diverse perspectives and experiences of the participants due to the potential truncation of their responses.

Another limitation stems from the reliance on email communication for survey dissemination. In the digital age, not all participants regularly check their emails, leading to missed survey invitations. This non-uniformity in email access can introduce a bias in the sample, as those who are less active in email correspondence might differ in significant ways from those who regularly engage with their email.

Conclusions

To the best of our knowledge, this study represents the inaugural endeavor to comprehensively investigate turnover intentions and job satisfaction exclusively among CRNAs within a single prominent healthcare institution with multiple locations. In conclusion, this study provides nuanced insights into the intricate web of factors influencing CRNAs' job satisfaction and turnover intentions. The training of new hires in a healthcare organization can incur substantial costs, potentially leading to negative consequences for the institution. These expenses not only pose financial challenges but also divert resources that could otherwise be invested back into the satisfaction and professional growth of the current CRNAs within the organization. By understanding these factors and their impact, healthcare organizations can develop targeted strategies to enhance job satisfaction, retain experienced professionals, and ultimately, ensure high-quality patient care.

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Appendix A

Kanter's Structural Theory of Power in Organization

Appendix B

Projected Timeline

Appendix C

Misener Nurse Practitioner Job Satisfaction Scale

Misener Nurse Practitioner Job Satisfaction Scale ©

Instructions:

The following is a list of items known to have varying levels of satisfaction among NPs. There may be items that do not pertain to you, however please answer it if you are able to assess your satisfaction with the item based on the employer's policy, i.e., if you needed it would it be there?

HOW SATISFIED ARE YOU IN YOUR CURRENT JOB AS A NURSE PRACTITIONER WITH RESPECT TO THE FOLLOWING FACTORS?

V.S. = Very Satisfied

S. = Satisfied

M.S. = Minimally Satisfied

M.D. = Minimally Dissatisfied

D. = Dissatisfied

V.D. = Very Dissatisfied

	V.S.	S.	MS.	M.D.	D.	V.D.
1. Vacation/Leave policy	6	5	4	3	2	1
2. Benefit package	6	5	4	3	2	1
3. Retirement plan	6	5	4	3	2	1
4. Time allotted for answering messages	6	5	4	3	2	1
5. Time allotted for review of lab and other test results	6	5	4	3	2	1
6. Your immediate supervisor	6	5	4	3	2	1
7. Percentage of time spent in direct patient care	6	5	4	3	2	1
8. Time allocation for seeing patient(s)	6	5	4	3	2	1
9. Amount of administrative support	6	5	4	3	2	1
10. Quality of assistive personnel	6	5	4	3	2	1
11. Patient scheduling policies and practices	6	5	4	3	2	1
12. Patient mix	6	5	4	3	2	1
13. Sense of accomplishment	6	5	4	3	2	1
14. Social contact at work	6	5	4	3	2	1
15. Status in the community	6	5	4	3	2	1
16. Social contact with your colleagues after work	6	5	4	3	2	1
17. Professional interaction with other disciplines	6	5	4	3	2	1

HOW SATISFIED ARE YOU IN YOUR CURRENT JOB AS A NURSE PRACTITIONER WITH:

V.S. = Very Satisfied
 S. = Satisfied
 M.S. = Minimally Satisfied

M.D. = Minimally Dissatisfied
 D. = Dissatisfied
 V.D. = Very Dissatisfied

	V.S.	S.	M.S.	M.D.	D.	V.D.
18. Support for continuing education (time and \$\$)	6	5	4	3	2	1
19. Opportunity for professional growth	6	5	4	3	2	1
20. Time off to serve on professional committees	6	5	4	3	2	1
21. Amount of involvement in research	6	5	4	3	2	1
22. Opportunity to expand your scope of practice	6	5	4	3	2	1
23. Interaction with other NPs including faculty	6	5	4	3	2	1
24. Consideration given to your opinion and suggestions for change in the work setting or office practice	6	5	4	3	2	1
25. Input into organizational policy	6	5	4	3	2	1
26. Freedom to question decisions and practices	6	5	4	3	2	1
27. Expanding skill level/procedures within your scope of practice	6	5	4	3	2	1
28. Ability to deliver quality care	6	5	4	3	2	1
29. Opportunities to expand your scope of practice and time to seek advanced education.	6	5	4	3	2	1
30. Recognition for your work from superiors	6	5	4	3	2	1
31. Recognition of your work from peers	6	5	4	3	2	1
32. Level of autonomy	6	5	4	3	2	1
33. Evaluation process and policy	6	5	4	3	2	1
34. Reward distribution	6	5	4	3	2	1
35. Sense of value for what you do	6	5	4	3	2	1
36. Challenge in work	6	5	4	3	2	1
37. Opportunity to develop and implement ideas.	6	5	4	3	2	1
38. Process used in conflict resolution	6	5	4	3	2	1
39. Amount of consideration given to your personal needs	6	5	4	3	2	1
40. Flexibility in practice protocols.	6	5	4	3	2	1
41. Monetary bonuses that are available in addition to your salary	6	5	4	3	2	1
42. Opportunity to receive compensation for services performed outside of your normal duties.	6	5	4	3	2	1
43. Respect for your opinion	6	5	4	3	2	1
44. Acceptance and attitudes of physicians outside of your practice (such as specialist you refer patients to)	6	5	4	3	2	1

Appendix D

Turnover Intention Scale (TIS-6)

DURING THE PAST 9 MONTHS.....

1	How often have you considered leaving your job?	Never	1-----2-----3-----4-----5	Always
2	How frequently do you scan the newspapers in search of alternative job opportunities?	Never	1-----2-----3-----4-----5	All the time
3	How satisfying is your job in fulfilling your personal needs?	Very satisfying	1-----2-----3-----4-----5	Totally dissatisfying
4	How often are you frustrated when not given the opportunity at work to achieve your personal work-related goals?	Never	1-----2-----3-----4-----5	Always
5	How often are your personal values at work compromised?	Never	1-----2-----3-----4-----5	Always
6	How often do you dream about getting another job that will better suit your personal needs?	Never	1-----2-----3-----4-----5	Always
7	How likely are you to accept another job at the same compensation level should it be offered to you?	Highly unlikely	1-----2-----3-----4-----5	Highly likely
8	How often do you look forward to another day at work?	Always	1-----2-----3-----4-----5	Never

Appendix E

IRB approval from CSUF and KP

APPROVAL NOTICE

*From the Institutional Review Board
California State University, Fullerton*

July 17, 2023

From: Dr. Matt Englar-Carlson, Chair
CSUF Institutional Review Board

To: PI: Alaina Yamamoto

Application No. HSR-22-23-431

Study Title: Exploring the Relationship Between Job Satisfaction and Turnover Intentions among Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists

Re: Initial Exempt Review

The forms you submitted to this office regarding the use of human participants in the above-referenced proposal have been reviewed by the Regulatory Compliance Coordinator and the Chair of the California State University, Fullerton, Institutional Review Board. Your proposal is determined to be Category 2.(i). Research that only includes interactions involving educational tests (cognitive, diagnostic, aptitude, achievement), survey procedures, interview procedures, or observation of public behavior (including visual or auditory recording) if at least one of the following criteria is met:

The information obtained is recorded by the investigator in such a manner that the identity of the human subjects cannot readily be ascertained, directly or through identifiers linked to the subjects;

The CSUF IRB has not evaluated your proposal for scientific merit, except to weigh the risk to the human participants and the aspects of the proposal related to potential risk and benefit. This approval notice does not replace any departmental or additional approvals which may be required.

In addition, all research personnel must follow the institutional safety guidelines outlined for CSUF's Presidential Directive 22. Additional information can be found in the [TITANS RETURN: COVID-19 Recovery](#) website.

It is of utmost importance that you strictly adhere to the guidelines for human participants and that you follow the plan/methodology/procedures described in your research proposal. Since your proposal was determined to be exempt, there is no further review or annual renewal required by the CSUF IRB. **However, any change in protocol or consent form procedure requires re-submission to the CSUF IRB for approval prior to implementation.** Additionally, the principal investigator must promptly report, in writing, any unanticipated or adverse events causing risks to research participants or others.

Please be advised that if you are seeking external funding for this proposal, the above-reference title should match exactly with the title submitted to the funding sponsor. Any changes in project title should be submitted to the CSUF IRB prior to implementation.

By copy of this notice, the chair of your department (and/or co-investigator) is reminded that their responsibility for being informed concerning research projects involving human participants in the department, and should review all protocols of such investigations as often as needed to ensure that the project is being conducted in compliance with our institutional policies and with DHHS regulations.

The institution has an Assurance on file with the Office of Human Research Protections. The Assurance Number is FWA00015384.

Cc: IRB Office
Sadeeka Al-Majid

InterOffice Memorandum

Armida Ayala

Armida Ayala, MHA, PhD
Director of Human Research Subjects Protection
Office/Institutional Review Board (IRB)

Appendix F

Table 1. Summary statistics of the sample demographics and employment (N=60).

Item	n (%)
1) Age	
31-40	16 (26.7)
40-45	1 (1.7)
46-50	20 (33.3)
51-60	19 (31.7)
61+	4 (6.7)
2) Gender	
Female	37 (61.7)
Male	22 (36.7)
Prefer not to say	1 (1.7)
3) Years of experience as a CRNA	
<1	1 (1.7)
1-3	4 (6.7)
4-7	8 (13.3)
8-10	8 (13.3)
11-15	13 (21.7)
16-20	11 (18.3)
21-30	14 (23.3)
31-40	1 (1.7)
4) Marital status	
Married	52 (86.6)
Divorced	4 (6.7)
Never married	4 (6.7)
5) Typical work shift	
8 hours	5 (8.3)
10 hours	8 (13.3)
12 hours	5 (8.3)
24 hours	2 (3.3)
8 and 10 hours	4 (6.7)
12 and 16 hours	3 (5.0)
16 and 24 hours	2 (3.3)
8, 10 and 12 hours	6 (10.0)
8, 10 and 16 hours	3 (5.0)
10, 12 and 24 hours	2 (3.3)
12, 16 and 24 hours	2 (3.3)
8, 10, 12, and 16 hours	9 (15.0)
8, 10, 12, 16 and 24 hours	2 (3.3)
12, 16 and 24 hours	2 (3.3)
Other	5 (8.3)
6) Employment status	
Full time	42 (70.0)
Part time	3 (5.0)

Per-diem	15 (25.0)
7) Plans for retirement in years	
<3	8 (13.4)
<5	7 (11.7)
>10	45 (75.0)

Appendix G

Turnover Intention Data

Table 2. Summary statistics of the turnover intention items (N=60).

Item	Mean (SD)
1) How often do you consider leaving your job?	2.7 (1.2)
2) How satisfying is your job in fulfilling your personal needs?	2.8 (1.0)
3) How often are you frustrated when not given the opportunity at work to achieve your personal goals?	2.4 (1.0)
4) How often do you dream of getting another job that will better suit your personal needs?	3.0 (1.3)
5) How likely are you to accept another job at the same compensation level should it be offered to you?	3.1 (1.5)
6) How often do you look forward to another day at work?	3.6 (1.2)
7) Overall	2.9 (1.0)

Average Turnover Intention Scores:

Appendix H

Correlation Matrix of the Turnover Intention items

Appendix I

Job Satisfaction Data

Appendix J

Subscales of MNPJSS

Appendix K

Table 4. Job Satisfaction Subscale Data with Years of Experience

Years of Experience	Factor 6		Factor 5		Factor 4		Factor 3		Factor 2		Factor 1	
	Mean	STDEV	Mean	STDEV	Mean	STDEV	Mean	STDEV	Mean	STDEV	Mean	STDEV
<1	7	0	15	0	12	0	35	0	38	0	53	0
1--3	10	3.56	16.25	5.5	15	9.42	36	4.55	37.5	9.54	38.75	21.08
4--7	12.25	2.71	17.88	1.36	15.38	4.57	34.88	4.32	40	5.04	40	10.84
8--10	14.75	1.39	19.25	1.16	20	3.66	38.5	3.12	46.25	6.94	51	14.05
11--15	13.1	2.84	17.62	2.79	16.46	5.22	34.85	3.93	42.23	7.2	45.54	10.75
16--20	15.73	2.83	18.64	3.01	18.91	6.47	37.72	5.76	44.64	8.14	49.1	15.08
21--30	13.79	4.12	16.64	3.71	17.36	6.37	33.21	6.91	38.86	9.21	36.57	14.73
>30	18	0	18	0	17	0	37	0	50	0	47	0
Overall Average	13.62	3.43	17.7	3.02	17.28	5.76	35.6	5.22	41.87	7.95	43.78	14.16
max score	18		24		30		48		60		78	
%	76		74		58		74		70		56	

Appendix L

Correlational Matrix on Job Satisfaction items

Appendix M

Table 3. Summary statistics of the fit of the best explanatory model*.

Satisfaction item	Effect	SE	t-value	p-value
Satisfaction with immediate supervisor	-0.15	0.04	-3.34	0.002
Satisfaction with patient scheduling policies and practices	-0.34	0.07	-4.69	<.001
Sense of accomplishment	-0.32	0.07	-4.82	<.001
Interaction with other NPs including faculty	-0.14	0.07	-2.12	0.04
Flexibility in practice protocols	-0.18	0.05	-3.34	0.002

*This model attained an R^2 of 0.82.